

Style in Language. – Cambridge: MIT Press, – 1960. – p. 350–377.

8. Leech, G. N. Language in literature: style and foregrounding / G.Leech – London and New York: Routledge, – 2013. – 183 p.

9. Malyuga E., Orlova S. Linguistic Pragmatics of Intercultural Professional and Business Communication / E.Malyuga, S.Orlova – Berlin: Springer, – 2017. – 145 p.

10. Nørgaard N., Busse B., Montoro R. Key Terms in Stylistics / N.Nørgaard, B.Busse, R.Montoro – London: A&C Black, – 2010. – 269 p.

11. Prague Studies in Mathematical Linguistics, Том 8. Eva Hajičová, Marie Těšitelová, Ján Horecký. Československá akademie věd. – Tuscaloosa: University of Alabama Press, – 1983 – 244 p.

12. Romanowski P. Intercultural Communicative Competence in English Language Teaching in Polish State Colleges / P. Romanowski – Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, – 2017. – 205 p.

13. Strachan J. Poetry / J. Strachan – Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, – 2011. – 256 p.

14. Van Peer. Stylistics and Psychology: Investigations in Foregrounding / Van Peer – London: Croom Helm, – 1986. – 220 p.

MINOR HUMAN TRAGEDY IN THE NOVELS OF MIKHAIL NUAYMAN

Seyidov R.R.

*The teacher of the chair "Russian and Oriental languages", Nakhchivan State University
PhD in Atatürk Arzurum University, Turkey
Nakhchivan, the Republic of Azerbaijan*

МАЛАЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКАЯ ТРАГЕДИЯ В РОМАНАХ МИХАИЛА НУАЙМАНА

Сейдов Р.Р.

*Преподаватель кафедры «Русский и восточные языки»,
Нахчыванский Государственный Университет
Доктор философии в Университете Ататюрк Арзурум, Турция
Нахчыван, Азербайджанская Республика*

Abstract

Already in the first quarter of the 20th century, the novella genre had a special place in Arabic literature. Researchers give different answers to the question "who is the first in the creation and application of this genre?" Nuayma takes the first place in the short story genre, because it was he who was able to revive real life here. In his novellas, Nuayma describes the life of her compatriots, who are often victims of illiteracy and superstition. Harmful customs and traditions are sharply criticized. It exposes the inner face of ambitious and profit-seeking people and opposes women's rightslessness.

Аннотация

Уже в первой четверти 20 века жанр новеллы занимал особое место в арабской литературе. При создании и применении этого жанра исследователи дают разные ответы на вопрос, «кому принадлежит первое место». Нуайма занимает первое место в жанре новеллы, ведь именно он смог оживить здесь реальную жизнь. В своих новеллах Нуайма описывает жизнь соотечественников, которые часто становятся жертвами пошлости и суеверий. Вредные обычаи и традиции подвергаются резкой критике. Он обнажает внутреннее лицо амбициозных и корыстолюбивых людей и выступает против женского бесправия.

Keywords: Mikhail Nuayman, novella, little man, tragedy, idea

Ключевые слова: Михаил Нуайман, новелла, маленький человек, трагедия, идея

Nuayma's creativity is multifaceted. His talent manifests itself equally successfully in all genres. Besides, novellas occupy a special place among his works. The writer's novellas are distinguished by features such as brevity, simplicity of expression, accuracy in describing the surrounding reality, variety of characters, plot dynamics and readability, subtle lyricism, and psychological richness.

The study of Mikhail Nuayma's novellas provides valuable material for illuminating the main aspects of modern Arabic literature.

Already in the first quarter of the 20th century, the novella genre had a special place in Arabic literature. Researchers give different answers to the question of

"who is the first" in the creation and application of this genre. Some give the right of primacy to Muhammad Lutfi Juma: His collection of stories called "In the Houses of the People" ("Fi bûyt en-nas") was published in 1904. Muhammad Rushdu Hasan stands at the head of writers who confirm that the first place belongs to M. L. Jume. He confirms his point of view in his research devoted to the creation of a short story in Arabic literature [3, p.90].

Another group of researchers considers Muhammad Teymur (1892-1921), known mainly as a playwright, to be the founder of the Arabic novella. The writer's first story "On the Train" was published in 1917. In the same year, his collection of stories "What

do my eyes see?" ("Ma Tarahu al-yyun") was published.

According to the supporters of the third position on this controversial issue, the first step in the creation of the novella genre in Arabic literature was taken by Mikhail Nuayman in 1914 with his story "His New Year". Abd al-Aziz Abd al-Majid commented on this point of view in his book "A Short Story in Modern Arabic Literature" ("al-Qissa al-Qasirah fi-l-adab al-arabi al-jadid"), published in English and Arabic. Despite the fact that Nuayman's first novella was published abroad - in the United States, it became very popular throughout the Arab world, because the work was "written in pure Arabic and the author created works that organically connect with the spiritual world of the Arabs." Lebanese critic Naim Hasan al-Yafi writes: "There is no doubt that the first place in the field of short stories belongs to Nuayman, who published his first story in 1914. He is the first novelist who has deep knowledge of literary forms and enriched the temple of art by writing his own stories for half a century" [2, p.90]. Nuayman takes the first place in the short story genre, because it was he who was able to revive real life here. Vital logic and depth of thought are integral features of these stories. The meaning of life is felt in these stories, created by the skillful hand of a skilled artist, they are also simple and understandable. The reader gets great pleasure while reading Nuayman's stories" - these words belong to modern Arab literary critic Ibrahim Abd al-Huri.

Nuayman emphasizes the importance of the impression that the ending of the novella will give, and at the same time shows the need for all parts of the work to form an organic unity. The writer himself strictly followed these rules. His novellas have a clear and fluent structure. Nuayman chooses more precise, concrete expressions to reveal the inner world of his heroes. The language of his novellas is clear and understandable. The writer talks about the most complex things in a language accessible to everyone (but not in a simple way). Also, despite rarely resorting to dialectics at this time, the norms of the literary language, to which Nuayman's novels follow all the rules, sound very natural even in the language of rural people.

Mikhail Nuayman's stories are collected in three main collections, but they can also be found in the writer's collection of articles ("The Voice of the World", "Light and Darkness", "Roads", etc.).

Mikhail Nuayman was able to publish his first collection of short stories only in 1937, a few years after returning to his homeland. All the stories included in the collection were written between 1914 and 1925 and were published in "as-Saih" newspaper and "al-Funun" magazine. After Nuayman's return to Lebanon, "Alf Leyla wa Laylat" ("1001 Nights") magazine publishes them on its pages.

Nuayman, who uses the traditional beginning of the Eastern fairy tale, calls his first collection of short stories: "It was or it was not." These stories describe the life of a Lebanese village and talk about the destructive effect of illiteracy and ignorance on the people's minds.

In 1956, Nuayman's second collection of stories called "Superiors" was published in Beirut. Its theme is

also taken from the Lebanese reality. The life of the village, the hard fate of simple workers - all this attracted the writer's attention.

Nuayman has created a whole garland of bright images. In the fate of his heroes, the contradictions of his time were reflected as in a mirror. Poor peasants who believe in the benevolence of landlords, representatives of the lower classes of the city, poor people who are ready to help those who are in trouble, profiteers, stingy statesmen and many other memorable images pass before the reader's eyes.

Humanism is the most important aspect of novelist Nuayman's creativity. In this regard, he was close to Chekhov, who loved "man not only because he is a highly intelligent, powerful and intelligent creature, but also because he is extremely weak, small, poor and helpless." [1, p. 69].

Nuayman's artistic skill lies in the fact that behind the fate of the person he describes in specific life conditions, the characteristic features of the social structure that causes injustice, inequality and hostility are visible.

Sadiq, the young hero of the story "Sadiq", always wants to lead a dignified and correct life. He was born in a poor family and was orphaned at an early age. A wealthy peasant takes pity on him and takes him to the pasture to feed his cows.

But the master demands from his shepherd not only honest labor, but also lies and hypocrisy at the command of the master. But Sadiq is honest and committed to his work. The enraged master beats him and throws him on the street. Soon, Sadiq finds another job and again makes a "mistake", or rather, tells the truth where he is asked to lie, and still remains without a piece of bread. Finally, Sadiq gets a chance to become a lawyer's driver. But he is still unlucky. As it happens, a lawyer hits a child with a car while driving. The lawyer orders all witnesses to remain silent about what happened. But when he cannot keep this secret, he puts the blame on Sadiq. The driver is sentenced to ten years in prison. Sadiq, whose hopes have been dashed, commits suicide. In his last letter it was written: "Cursed be the world that has no place for the faithful!" [5, p. 190].

The writer skillfully reveals the inner world of his heroes, demonstrates the contrast between Sadiq's pure intentions and bright dreams and the insidious and hypocritical nature of the current structure that deprives people of an honorable life path.

Sadiq encounters different people in his hard life. Here is a rich master who is ready to beat a destitute orphan to death for a few pennies, or to cheat a friend, a rich widow who only competes with her rival - the minister's wife, and thinks of ways to outdo her, blames an innocent, defenseless person for the crime they have committed. . By putting these cruel, lying and greedy people against people who make a living with lawful labor, Nuayman not only shows the misfortune of a person, but also reveals the flaws of the social structure where lies prevail over the truth. Thus, the writer is satisfied with showing the balance of forces in society, making the reader think about looking for a way out.

The story is instructive, kind of a cautionary tale with a modern theme. His instructive style of writing is noticeable from the beginning, which is already unique

and somewhat funny: "There are so many funny things that happen in life that you can't stop counting them. One of the incidents is related to names. A number of people carry their names as if they are mocking themselves. For example, let's take the name Jamila (beautiful). How many girls are given this name, but there are those who are so ugly that they almost remind of the devil himself, or when you pass by someone named Wardat (rose), it is as if you are passing by a pile of dung. When several Asads (lions) see a rabbit, they run away without looking back, it is easier to take a bone from the dog's hand than to extract a (generous) penny or two from some Karims. There are certain people (honor, conscience) who cannot be trusted even with the skin of an onion..." [2, p. 79]. But Sadiq, according to the author, is an exception, "as the skin suits the body", so his name suits him. However, the hero's name, which is so suitable for him, brings him immense difficulties, which ultimately leads to his death.

The story "Abu Batta" tells about the hard life of the poor. Abu Batta is the strongest porter of Beirut, "one of the poor workers who wanders around the city, and in fact carries the entire trading life of this city on his back. Wealthy merchants look down on these people, they treat them as indifferently as their old slippers" [1, p. 7].

Abu Batta is old and his legs are sick. He was stung by a scorpion when he was still a child, and the swelling of the poison remained in his leg for life. Swollen thick veins "were intertwined all along the leg, they were so blue that it seemed as if they were filled with blue slime. Most of all, they swelled in hot weather and on days when Abu Batta was carrying a heavy load" [6, p. 9]. During his hard and difficult life, he was able to collect only eleven pounds of gold coins. And now a certain shop owner is looking for a porter to carry a heavy cask full of white oil. No one agrees to carry such a heavy burden except eighty-year-old Abu Batta. Neither the merchant nor the passers-by are interested in the old man's health. Even when he could not bear the weight of the barrel and fell to the ground, trembling from weakness, the master only cared about the barrel containing a thousand pounds of oil. Abu Batta thinks a lot about life, sees all the contradictions of life, feels all its injustices in his soul. "Truly, the lie is in the yeast in the world, and the truth of an honest person turns into a liar's lie first and last, because the truth has become a kind of madness, the reason for insult that leads to death, or to avoid people" [4, p. 11]. Abu Batta and Sadiq are different people, but their thoughts about life are very similar.

Nuayman appreciates the spiritual qualities of Abu Batta. Eternal need and humiliation did not change his character. Like the other porters of the city, he has suffered so much that he doesn't even think about defending his human dignity. For example, Nuayman created the image of a writer who observes the life of people like Abu Batta. He often talks with Abu Batta and helps him with money. However, the writer does not even think of explaining his human rights to the old porter. When Abu Batta dies, one of his sons, who inherited his father's rare physical strength, takes his place, and it all begins again.

The story "Superiors" is closer to Nuayman's creative style. Like other works dedicated to the life of Lebanese villagers, Nuayman's work is written with sensitive love and compassion for people. Suffering and lonely people who are unable to fight against injustice... They come to life in front of us on the pages of Mikhail Nuayman's stories...

Abu Rashid and his wife Umm Rashid are no exception. The entrepreneur sends them a message that he will come to divide the product. It was necessary to welcome the master in a solemn way, with a festive table. There was nothing in their house except a few tin plates, clay cups, a pair of wooden spoons and a low table. Abu Rashid and Umm Rashid had an only son named Rashid. The child does not have even a single toy, the most dear to him in the world are his kid named Ifrit and rooster named Sultan. The child feeds them, takes care of them and is proud of them. That is why, despite his parents' reprimands, Rashid does not agree to slaughtering either the rooster or the kid to entertain the master, to whom his family owes three thousand kuras. But if this year's harvest is twice less than last year's, how to pay the debt? The master comes to the village in a car with his wife and Rashid-year-old daughter. Villagers invite them home. But the master's French-speaking wife refuses to enter the poor hut with her fashionable clothes. He doesn't even want to hear about eating from a tin plate with a wooden spoon. Abu Rashid and Umm Rashid are insulted.

Nuayman writes: "Now they would rather die from this shame without hesitation." But the villagers do not dare to express their grievances. The master demands his debt from them. Abu Rashid explains that he collected a small amount of crops because of the drought. "This is your business - says the master - I don't care about it. Tomorrow I will send my driver to pick up my share of crops." When the guests are about to leave, the master's daughter tells her mother in French that she wants to take the rooster and the kid with her. All this time, Rashid was playing with them without paying attention to anyone. Her mother answers the girl that "whatever your heart desires, it will be yours." The owners take the rooster and the kid and leave. Although Abu Rashid and Umm Rashid were hardworking and kind people, they were also public and superstitious. For example, he takes a handful of grains in his hand and thinks in his heart that if the number of grains comes out even, they will stay on this land and the master will not demand usury from them, or if he comes out alone, he and his family will be kicked out of the land they occupied. Abu Rashid and Umm Rashid used to obey. When the master's wife ordered him to take the rooster and the kid to the car, Abu Rashid knew very well that he was depriving his child of his only joy, but he obeyed the order without saying a word. His wife was obediently silent.

Another couple is a cruel lord and his wife. They believe that with wealth, any evil can be removed. The image of the rich man, who does not ignore the sufferings of Keridli, is reminiscent of the image of the gentleman in the famous poem "Farmer" by the great Azerbaijani poet M.A. Sabir. Nuayman notes that modern "civilized" gentlemen are even more cruel and greedy

than the previous "past" masters. The author mentions in the story that the master's late father was a kinder and simpler person. It reminds him to sit together with the peasants, share the poor table with them, and not take usury from anyone. In fact, the deceased master and his current master, as well as his family, which includes his youngest daughter, are among the "superiors" in the eyes of the peasant. Nuayman reveals the inner face of these "superior" people - those who have no heart and conscience, who "eat from porcelain dishes and use knives and forks in a modern fashion". Although the writer calls them "superiors", he uses this word with sarcasm and irony.

The reader feels disgusted with the hard-heartedness of such people, and feels sensitive and compassionate towards the hard fate of others. Nuayman opposes the oppression of the rich over the poor by exposing the unjust laws that leave the peasants in a state of disenfranchisement. With the power of the artistic word, he stigmatizes the privileged classes who show indifference to the needs of the common people.

Nuayman's story "The Gift" also has a deep tragic content. His hero Banna Masud works in construction. This is a young man with "a strong back, broad chest, strong shoulders, strong legs and hands." He has a secret dream for a long time - to give his wife a mirror. Therefore, he works from dawn to dusk, does not eat sugary food, and saves every penny. Finally, he can collect thirty pounds. On the way home, Masud wants to calculate his money and make sure that the diamond will be enough to buy a mirror. After all, the small shard of a mirror he found in a garbage heap near a wealthy house cannot be considered a mirror. Every time he sees his wife looking at this broken mirror, the sufferings of Masud make the reader ache for the fate of this young man.

Mikhail Nuayman's rich life experience did not allow him to uncover the deep roots of social contradictions in human destiny and deeds, to reveal them in specific circumstances. Any typical social event is not presented in the form of an abstract generalization in Nuayman's novels, but in a concrete landscape, in the fate and lives of concrete people. This is why his works are convincing and vital. As mentioned, many heroes of Nuayman are not ready to fight for a better life, for the protection of human rights. In Nuayman's stories, there are open calls to fight against the existing structure. Depicting life correctly, the author makes people think about the flaws of modern society.

In several of her works, Nuayman talks about the difficult fate of Arab immigrants in America. He exposes the flaws of the western civilization and works for the Arab emigrants to return to their homeland as soon as possible. It describes their alienation, the Arabs being changed and transformed by the corrupting influence of the American way of life.

References

1. Golubkov, V. (1990) The mastery of A.P. Chekhov. M., 190 p.
2. Dolinina, A. (2001). Gogol in Arabic literature. - Sat. "Gogol. Articles and materials», L., 280 p.
3. Dolinina, A. (2003). From the prehistory of realism in new Arabic literature. - Sat. "Problems of the formation of realism in the literature of the East". M., 1964.
4. Dolinina, A. (2007). Essays on the history of Arabic literature of the new time. Egypt and Syria. Publicistics. M., 290 p.
5. Al-Kayali, M. (2011) About modern Arabic literature. - Sat. "Modern Arabic literature". M., 310 p.
6. Konrad, N. (2006). The problem of realism and literature of the East. - Sat. "Problems of the formation of realism in the literature of the East". M., 340 p.